

RADx-UP Evaluation Report Executive Summary

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Executive Summary

RADx-UP Program Evaluation Overview

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) program was launched to improve access to rapid, accurate COVID-19 diagnostics among underserved populations that are disproportionately affected by the coronavirus pandemic across the United States (US).

The RADx-UP program is comprised of a Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) which provides technical support to all the projects within the RADx-UP consortium: **144** RADx-UP large award research projects (herein referred to as RADx-UP research projects), **25** Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) projects (herein referred to as RP2 projects), and **70** Community Collaboration Grant (C2G) projects (herein referred to as C2G projects).

The four specific aims of the RADx-UP program, specifically for the CDCC consortium, are to:

- 1) Create a community-centered, flexible program infrastructure
- 2) Support a participatory and inclusive community engagement program
- 3) Support research projects with COVID-19 testing guidance and emerging science.
- 4) Collect, harmonize, integrate, and disseminate data to scientific and local communities.

The comprehensive evaluation plan developed for the RADx-UP program assesses how the CDCC program activities improve the RADx-UP program's effectiveness, performance, and community engagement, helping to understand how the CDCC met its aims. Additionally, the evaluation plan was designed to comprehensively assess the RADx-UP program's projects' (RADx-UP research, RP2 and C2G) implementation processes, outcomes, and impact. The primary purpose of this report is to describe key evaluation findings across the RADx-UP program from launch through February 2024.

Evaluation Methods, Analysis and Components

Supported by guiding frameworks which include the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM), the Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation, and Maintenance Framework (RE-AIM) and the Social Ecological Model (SEM), the RADx-UP Tracking and Evaluation team used a mixed-methods approach to evaluate the RADx-UP program’s processes, outcomes, and impacts through the following evaluation components as described in the table below:

Component	Purpose	Analytical Procedures
RADx-UP Research Project Evaluation		
Publication Tracking	Assess research productivity. Data generated are disseminated on the RADx-UP public website and used for other component analyses.	* Monthly tracking of all RADx-UP-funded research products through surveys and automated database searches. 1,011 products have been tracked through February 2024.
Bibliometric Analysis	Quantitatively assess the scientific impacts of RADx-UP publication and citation data.	Used data from 196 RADx-UP publications tracked through March 31, 2023, to measure publication and citation impacts across diverse project characteristics.
Network Analysis	Identify patterns of scientific collaborations among authors to assess scientific outputs and impacts.	Conducted a network analysis of topic and co-authorship networks from 196 RADx-UP publications tracked through March 31, 2023.
Content Analysis	Identify the key themes emerging from RADx-UP publications.	Through July 2023, reviewers identified study characteristics, translational science benefits of testing and vaccination and thematic categories of impacts across 231 RADx-UP projects’ publications.
Project Implementation Survey	Assess the Successes, Challenges, Reach, Collaboration, Impacts, and Sustainability of Project Implementation Activities	Mixed-methods survey was administered to 84 research projects’ academic representatives from 2022 to 2023.
Project Interviews		Interviews were conducted with 24 community and academic partners associated with 32 research projects in 2023.
Pandemic Caseload Analysis	Show RADx-UP testing reach impacts among socially vulnerable populations by predicting testing rates during the COVID-19 Delta and Omicron variant caseload surges.	Utilized RADx-UP research projects’ COVID-19 tests data (Delta, n= 31 projects; Omicron, n= 37 projects) and publicly available caseload and vaccinations rates data to identify 1) trend/case patterns between COVID-19 testing and positivity counts and 2) significant predictors of COVID-19 cases during variant surges.
Statistical-Spatial Analysis	Assess the benefits of collaborating with community-based organizations for	Utilized RADx-UP Common Data Elements (CDEs) (26 projects; 115,645 tests across 3,223 codes) and Project Implementation Survey data to assess the

	increasing the reach of RADx-UP program testing in underserved areas	benefits of collaborating with community-based organizations for RADx-UP testing reach between communities of high and low social vulnerability index scores.
Agent-Based Modeling	Understand potential impacts of RADx-UP testing reach within communities served	Utilized RADx-UP CDEs across 26 research projects to depict differences in duration of transmission chains among communities with and without RADx-UP testing.
Pilot Projects Evaluation		
C2G Evaluation	Evaluate projects' activities, outcomes, impacts, and use of CDCC support and resources	Repeated cross-sectional design and a mixed methods approach to collect data from bi-annual surveys and 6-months after program close-out interviews from 70 C2G projects.
RP2 Evaluation		Repeated cross-sectional design and a mixed methods approach to collect data from bi-monthly surveys from 25 RP2 projects.
CDCC Evaluation		
CDCC Evaluation	Assess: 1) the efficiency of CDCC processes; 2) the perceived value of their deliverables; and 3) the satisfaction with CDCC service provision to support RADx-UP projects.	Mixed-methods survey sent annually to 29 RADx-UP projects academic representatives in 2023.

Key Findings

Who did the RADx-UP program reach?

- Across the RADx-UP program projects, the **five** most frequently reached populations were **Hispanic/Latino, Black/African American, American Indian/Alaskan Native, Hawaii Pacific Islander, and Asian.**

What community outreach strategies for recruitment and retention did the RADx-UP program use? What were the challenges?

- **RADx-UP program projects effectively recruited participants** and promoted COVID-19 awareness using face-to-face recruitment, social media, text messages, and project websites.
- Although projects were ultimately successful in addressing COVID-19 testing and other community needs, some also experienced challenges related to recruitment and retention such as the pool of unvaccinated people to recruit from and participants' struggle to monitor symptoms.

What were the reach and impacts of RADx-UP COVID-19 testing activities?

RADx-UP Projects' Testing Reach and Impacts

- Between June 2020 and November 2023, **446,268** COVID-19 tests were submitted via the NIH RADx-UP Common Data Elements (CDE).

Figure graphic developed and designed by the [RADx-UP CDCC Communications Team for RADx-UP](#)

- More than half of RADx-UP research projects ($n=47/82$; 57.5 percent) reported distributing COVID-19 tests which include on-site testing and/or self-testing kits.
- RADx-UP research projects used a **variety of strategies to improve testing uptake** such as health communication messaging ($n=36/83$; 43 percent), providing multiple testing locations ($n=25/83$; 30 percent), employing community health workers (CHW) ($n=24/83$; 29 percent), and using social media ($n=20/83$; 24 percent).
- Using **culturally responsive and tailored intervention strategies**, including leveraging community partnerships to deliver intervention, also increased testing uptake ($n=28/83$; 34 percent).

Statistical Modeling of RADx-UP COVID-19 Testing Reach and Impacts

- **Statistical-spatial analysis** findings indicated that RADx-UP research projects collaborating with community-based organizations (CBOs) to increase participant access to project sites, health care, and/or social services, extended their reach to areas characterized by high social vulnerability index (SVI) scores.
 - Projects in high SVI areas that engaged CBOs distributed a higher number of COVID-19 tests (9.5 times more tests; 73.8 versus 7.8 tests) when compared to those projects in high SVI areas that did not collaborate with CBOs.
 - 73.8 predicted tests in projects engaging with CBOs in high SVI communities compared to 12.1 predicted tests among projects engaging with CBOs in low SVI communities.
- **Pandemic Caseload Analysis** revealed interesting trends in RADx-UP COVID-19 testing, and positive case counts during the Delta and Omicron surge periods. RADx-UP testing rates and positive test cases followed a similar pattern with a peak occurring around the end of August 2021 during the Delta surge and in the middle of January 2022 during the Omicron surge. On occasion when caseloads surged, RADx-UP projects tended to enroll more participants. Projects within the RADx-UP program were able to increase participant enrollment and testing during the Delta and Omicron surges of positive COVID-19 cases.
- **Agent-based Modeling Analysis** highlighted the impact of RADx-UP testing on reducing infection rates across underserved populations. This finding suggests that expanding testing outreach to medium risk communities could significantly reduce infection rates compared to low and high-risk communities. When modeling and comparing the maximum possible infections with and without RADx-UP testing by plotting the Probability Density Function (PDF) of peak infections obtained, with RADx-UP testing, the mean peak infection was estimated to be around 20 people, whereas without RADx-UP testing, the mean peak infection is estimated to be around 90 people. This analysis provided further evidence that RADx-UP testing has played an important role in minimizing infection within targeted communities.

RP2 Testing Reach

- RP2, which funds small, manageable research studies for 12 months, enrolled **4,086** participants.
- RP2 projects used novel strategies and interventions such as software applications, vending machines, and COVID-flu combination testing to reach underserved populations and settings.
- A total of **4,948** COVID-19 tests were administered throughout the program period.

Figure graphic developed and designed by the RADx-UP CDCC Communications Team for the RP2 program

C2G Testing Reach

- C2G provides direct costs to support community partners to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives.
- C2G projects testing efforts reached approximately **120,000** people within their communities.
- C2G project activities that increased testing access and uptake included generating communication materials for COVID-19 testing, engaging trusted community members and organizations to facilitate testing, and providing training and education.

How did the RADx-UP program engage and collaborate with communities?

- **Effective Multi-level Partnerships:** Almost two-thirds ($n=52/80$; 65 percent) of RADx-UP research projects formed community-based partnerships to overcome implementation barriers, address recruitment challenges, and build trust within target communities.
 - More than half ($n=19/29$; 66 percent) of RP2 projects and most ($n=49/55$; 89 percent) C2G projects reported partnerships with community-based organizations/non-profit organizations.
 - **Community-based partners actively contributed** to RADx-UP projects' planning and implementation, engaging in outreach, recruitment, retention, study design, data collection, and utilizing findings to enhance project implementation.
- **Active Community Committees:** Community advisory boards ($n=38/83$; 46 percent) played a crucial role in providing guidance on testing strategies and tailoring interventions.

How satisfied were RADx-UP program projects with CDCC services and what are the opportunities for improvement?

Overall, RADx-UP program projects were satisfied with CDCC administrative support and responsiveness.

- **RADx-UP-** most RADx-UP research projects were satisfied with CDCC's staff professionalism ($n=31/35$; 89 percent), helpfulness ($n=30/35$; 86 percent), ease of accessing service support ($n=30/35$; 86 percent), promptness of services ($n=29/35$; 83 percent) and implementation of project feedback ($n=28/35$; 80 percent).
 - Research projects need **more clarity on expectations** for (and changes in) CDCC workstream goals, processes, and services, especially around close-out activities and other end-of-grant support.
- **RP2-** projects were satisfied with CDCC's administrative support with respect to cultural competency and responsiveness, knowledge in resolving project issues, onboarding and training resources, and response time to requests.
 - To reduce challenges because of the short funding period and rapid funding cycles, projects suggested that the NIH and CDCC could **extend grant funding periods** for future pilot programs.

- **C2G-** Overall, **85 percent** (n=49/55) of C2G projects reported satisfaction with CDCC administrations' support.
 - Suggested areas to improve CDCC support include **simplifying** the application process, **increasing flexibility** in some of the grant requirements, and **supporting collaboration** among projects.

What were some of the RADx-UP programs' benefits for and impacts on communities?

- **Community and Public Health Benefits:** The RADx-UP program provides testing in underserved communities, particularly valuable during times of strained public health resources. Using community engagement strategies (for example, understanding barriers and facilitators of uptake, using community health workers to deliver culturally tailored telehealth education sessions) helped to increase COVID-19 testing uptake and accessibility among different target communities.
- **Economic Benefits:** Over half (**56 percent**) of the RADx-UP research projects provided economic benefits, primarily by minimizing test costs (n=38/83; **46 percent**), time to complete tests (n=33/83; **40 percent**), and time to receive test results (n=28/83; **34 percent**).
- **Pandemic Preparedness:** Survey results suggest that many RADx-UP research projects' activities (n=59/82; **72 percent**), especially **COVID-19 testing** (n=43/47; **91 percent**), are **agile and replicable**, contributing to **improved pandemic preparedness** in underserved communities.

What were the implementation successes achieved by RADx-UP projects?

RADx-UP Projects Increased COVID-19 Testing Uptake

- **Testing Accessibility and Procurement:** Most RADx-UP research projects (n=39/47; **83 percent**) indicated success in increasing testing accessibility. Many (n=10/15; **67 percent**) that experienced challenges were able to **easily connect with the CDCC for support to mitigate procurement challenges**.
- **Testing Resources and Promotional Strategies:** RADx-UP research projects most frequently utilized a variety of **community-based outreach strategies** such as utilizing health communication messaging (n=36/83; **43 percent**), providing testing locations (n=25/83; **30**

percent), employing community health workers (CHW) (n=24/83; 29 percent), and using social media (n=20/83; 24 percent) to improve testing and vaccination uptake.

- **Culturally Tailored Approaches:** RADx-UP research projects (n=28/83; 34 percent) reported employing culturally responsive strategies as an approach to increase testing uptake, such as hiring staff from the community, providing translation services, and crafting culturally appropriate messaging.

Implementation Successes from RADx-UP Research Project Partnerships

- **Active Community Engagement:** The active involvement of community advisory boards (n=38/83; 46 percent) and steering committees (n=5/83; 6 percent) played a crucial role in providing guidance on testing strategies, tailoring interventions, and facilitating bi-directional learning between academic and community partners.
- **Building Community Capacity:** Community-based partners actively contributed to research projects' planning, implementation, and dissemination of findings. RADx-UP research projects developed research capacity of community-based partners by providing research skills training (n=28/83; 34 percent) and leadership opportunities (n=46/83; 55 percent).
- **Cultural Responsiveness:** RADx-UP research projects demonstrated cultural responsiveness by employing diverse staff (n=49/83; 59 percent), providing training in culturally responsive care (n=37/83; 44.6 percent), and using plain language in research products (n=35/83; 42 percent).
- **Addressing Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) needs:** Beyond COVID-19 interventions, a few research projects' partnership collaborations (n=2) addressed broader social needs, such as cash assistance and food distribution, with many (n=52/80; 65 percent) reporting that they connected participants to healthcare and social services.

What were the implementation challenges faced by projects within the RADx-UP program?

- **COVID-19 Testing Supply and Uptake:** Eighteen (18) RADx-UP research projects faced testing supply issues, staffing challenges, changes/restrictions in FDA and NIH testing guidelines (also experienced by RP2 projects), and difficulties in restocking specific testing kit

brands. Uptake challenges included low attendance at walk-up clinics, minimal engagement in repeat testing, and testing fatigue.

- **Project Administration:** Twenty-eight (28) RADx-UP research projects and some C2G projects described dealing with staff shortages, turnover, limited capacity, and funding.
- **Challenges with Participant Engagement:** Eighteen (18) RADx-UP research projects reported facing recruitment and retention challenges due to waning COVID-19 interest, logistical issues, and staff constraints. Of the 13 RP2 projects that reported challenges, the most common were related to enrollment and testing reporting.
- **Partnership Coordination and Community Capacity:** Eleven (11) RADx-UP research projects described difficulties in coordinating and engaging diverse stakeholders, securing support, and addressing resource constraints. RADx-UP program projects (RADx-UP research, RP2, and C2G) encountered capacity limitations, particularly in engaging partners and community-based organizations.
- **Data-Related:** Thirty-two (32) research projects described challenges with data collection, analysis, and dissemination due to the rapid evolution of the pandemic, COVID-19 fatigue, staffing shortages, and lack of data science expertise.

What types of scholarly and non-scholarly products did the RADx-UP program projects develop?

- **Number of Products:** As of early 2024, T&E tracked 712 RADx-UP program scholarly products (286 publications, 342 conference presentations, 81 extramural grants, 3 intramural grants) and 299 non-scholarly products.
- **Most Disseminated Products:** Most RADx-UP products were conference presentations ($n=342$), followed by non-scholarly products (e.g., websites, blog posts, radio shows, videos, news articles, etc. ($n=299$), and scholarly publications ($n=286$).

- **Comparison across 2021-23** : RADx-UP program scholarly products increased by **52 percent (+94 products)** in 2022 and **18 percent (+32 products)** in 2023 when compared to 2021 (**180 products**).

What did RADx-UP program scholarly collaboration for research dissemination look like?

- As of March 31, 2023, the network analysis of **196** RADx-UP publications which assessed scientific collaboration showed **779** authors grouped into **34** clusters (co-authorship components).
- Consistent with findings in 2022, we observed relatively few scientific collaborations across program projects.
- **Non-academic co-authors** were present in most clusters (**n=27/34; 89 percent**) of the RADx-UP publication network.
- **Community outreach** emerged as the **most central publication topic characteristic** and contributed most to holding the publications network together such that it connected topics that might not otherwise be connected. This highlights the importance of the space that RADx-UP provided for community-engaged research to thrive.

How did RADx-UP publications advance knowledge on COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-engaged research?

Content Analysis

- **Most common key learning categories** from **231** publications: 1) *social, ethical, and behavioral factors (SEBI) influencing testing (n=39)*, 2) *vaccination (n=48)*, and 3) *impacts of collaborative partnerships and community engagement (n=44)*.
- **SEBI factors influencing testing and vaccination uptake**: Publications reviewed noted disparities in testing and vaccination hesitancy, motivation, access, and uptake exist among diverse underserved populations. Initiatives like in-reach and outreach through clinics, mobile units, reduced-cost/free testing and vaccination, employer-sponsored resources, and at-home testing improved access and uptake to COVID-19 testing and vaccination.

- **Structural Barriers to Testing and Vaccination:** Seventeen (17) publications cited different structural barriers to testing. These barriers include transportation or driving times, location of centers or services, inflexible work schedules, fear of losing employment while getting tested, wait times or scheduling, fear of exposure while waiting to be tested, and the cost of testing. Thirteen (13) publications cited one or more structural barriers to COVID-19 vaccination that were parallel to testing barriers.
- **Impact of Community Engagement and Collaborative Partnerships:** Twenty-five (n=25/44) publications coded under *impacts of collaborative partnerships and community engagement* described these impacts in detail within the following areas:
 - Utilize multi-sector partnerships to implement, adapt, and promote testing or vaccination.
 - Strengthen recruitment and data collection.
 - Improve community capacity for research and community workforce development.
 - Inform health messaging, outreach and dissemination strategies.
 - Use community advisory board and community-based participatory research methods to guide research implementation.
 - Build sustainable trusted relationships within communities.
 - Evaluate the impacts and strengths of community engagement.

What were some of the bibliometric impacts from RADx-UP publications?

- RADx-UP publications (n=196) focused on diverse communities and populations with the three most frequent being **Hispanic/Latino (n=46 publications)**, **Black/African American (n=31 publications)**, and **children/adolescents (n=26 publications)**.
- The bibliometric analysis found a **strong research influence** of RADx-UP publications.
 - From the Scopus database, **189** articles had **966** citations.
 - Research influence as measured by time- and field- normalized relative citation ratio (RCR) scores indicates that RADx-UP publications had a **greater-than-typical citation rate** compared to NIH-funded papers in the same field and year.

- Altmetric data such as mentions and citations in news, social media, and policy also showed that RADx-UP program findings from 194 publications translated beyond scholarly audiences.

To what extent will RADx-UP program impacts be sustained?

RADx-UP Research Projects

- More than half of RADx-UP research projects (n=57/82; 70 percent) indicated that their community engagement strategies will continue and almost a third (n=27/82; 33 percent) have secured or will seek additional funding to sustain other project activities and interventions.
- Additionally, some research projects (n=39/57; 68 percent) indicated that priority populations will continue to have access to project-related healthcare and social services.

RP2

- RP2 projects plan to use their project data as evidence to justify feasibility when applying for additional funding.

C2G

- Organizations affiliated with C2G projects reported that they continued COVID-19 testing and education activities including partnerships within their communities.

CDCC

- Through its *Sankofa Project* Initiative, the CDCC is committed to leaving a rich legacy of data, published articles, resources and toolkits including best practices for community-engaged research.
- To date, the *Sankofa Project* Taskforce has: 1) engaged the consortium - developing and refining learning categories; defining audiences; and identifying proposed legacy products; 2) created an asset catalog – creating an inventory of all current RADx-UP products (to be updated as products are developed in 2024); and 3) curation of the catalog.
- Future steps include dissemination activities and contextualization of products for future use of products.

Conclusions and Implications

- Across multiple analyses, key evaluation findings show that the RADx-UP program improved COVID-19 testing access and uptake across the US, its territories, and Tribal Nations while strengthening academic and community partnerships for public health programming and research.
- Additionally, the RADx-UP program advanced scientific knowledge about COVID-19 testing and community engaged research while creating a space for collaborative research to thrive. The consortia approach to supporting many projects was largely successful, with most program projects indicating satisfaction or high satisfaction overall with CDCC support and resources.
- Many of the program activities that benefit underserved communities will continue in some capacity after project closeout. Additionally, the knowledge gained from the initiative will be made available to inform future community and public health initiatives further extending the RADx-UP program impact.
- Evaluation findings indicate that the RADx-UP program has made and continues to make significant progress towards achieving its aims to create a flexible infrastructure that is responsive to projects' needs, support a participatory and inclusive community engagement program, disseminate findings to multiple audiences, and contribute to scientific knowledge on COVID-19 testing and community-engaged research.

